

Ex-vivo experimental strategies for assessing unconstrained shoulder biomechanics: a scoping review protocol

Authors

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Detailed search strategy

Search Narrative

- **Overall search structure:**
 - (ex-vivo/artificial material/cadaver)*
 - AND (simulator/testing/device/instruments)*
 - AND (Shoulder/shoulder muscles)*
 - AND (biomechanics/forces)*
- **Iterations:** We started with 3 search blocks (*cadaver AND shoulder AND biomechanics*) but found results too unspecific and broad. Hence we added a fourth block (*simulator terms*). Anatomic model terms can be found in both the *cadaver* and the *simulator* block as it suits both and returned a few extra results.
- **No limits** were applied. Searches were done exactly as described.
- **Seed paper**
 - PubMed: search found 16/16
24170552[pmid] OR 21567454[pmid] OR 12038616[pmid] OR 29741391[pmid] OR 9524340[pmid] OR 17433334[pmid] OR 22626997[pmid] OR 9070535[pmid] OR 11603523[pmid] OR 7657685[pmid] OR 8982143[pmid] OR 21330155[pmid] OR 7931787[pmid] OR 1613626[pmid] OR 15726089[pmid] OR 30514628[pmid]
 - Embase.com: search found 16/16
24170552:ui OR 21567454:ui OR 12038616:ui OR 29741391:ui OR 9524340:ui OR 17433334:ui OR 22626997:ui OR 9070535:ui OR 11603523:ui OR 7657685:ui OR 8982143:ui OR 21330155:ui OR 7931787:ui OR 1613626:ui OR 15726089:ui OR 30514628:ui
- **Text mining tools** used to assess seed papers during search drafting phase:
 - PubMed Reminer: <https://hgserver2.amc.nl/cgi-bin/miner/miner2.cgi>
 - Yale MeSH Analyzer: <http://mesh.med.yale.edu/>

- **Terms discussed in team and omitted**

- adsorption kinetics
- agility
- altered gravity
- 'apparatus and instruments'
- Arthrometry, Articular
- biomass
- Bionics
- Biophysics
- blood viscosity
- body mass
- body movement
- body remains
- bone mass
- Cell Movement
- Compliance
- computational fluid dynamics
- Computer Simulation
- contraction stress
- Coriolis Force (under motion)
- Decompression, Explosive
- 'deltoid ligament'
- 'devices'/exp (selected exceptions in the search)
- dry mass
- Elastic Modulus
- Elasticity
- elbow flexion
- Electroosmosis
- fat free mass
- fat mass
- Flexural Strength
- flow kinetics
- gelatinization
- gravitational stress
- Hardness
- Hardness Tests
- heart left ventricle mass
- high-fidelity patient simulator
- high-fidelity simulator
- hydrodynamics
- Hydrostatic Pressure
- involuntary movement
- joint characteristics and functions
- joint function
- joint limitation
- Joint Prosthesis
- 'lifting effort'
- limb movement
- Linearization
- Locomotion
- Lower Body Negative Pressure
- Manikins
- Materials Testing
- mechanobiological
- Mechanotransduction, Cellular
- microgravity
- molecular mechanics
- movement (physiology)
- Muscle Contraction
- Muscle insertion
- muscle tone
- musculoskeletal modeling
- Organ Motion
- Orthodontic Friction
- Osmosis
- Osmotic Pressure
- Partial Pressure
- passive movement
- patient mobility
- patient simulator
- photodynamics
- physical mobility
- plasticity
- Porosity
- pressure and tension
- Prosthesis Design
- Prosthesis Failure
- proton motive force
- Pulsatile Flow (under motion)
- quantum mechanics
- rigidity
- robotic
- robotic surgery simulator
- Robotics
- rotator cuff injuries
- shear rate
- shock wave
- smooth muscle tone
- sputum viscosity
- surface stress
- surgical simulator
- synkinesis
- synthetic bone graft
- Taxis Response
- Tensile Strength
- thermodynamics
- Torsion
- Vacuum
- Vapor Pressure
- velocity
- Vibration
- virtual reality simulator
- viscoelasticity
- viscosity
- Visible Human Projects
- voluntary movement
- wall stress
- weight
- Weight-Bearing
- weightlessness

Database searching

PubMed, 12/07/2021: 2164 hits

("Models, Anatomic"[Mesh:NoExp] OR "Cadaver"[Mesh:NoExp] OR "In Vitro Techniques"[Mesh:NoExp] OR "Cartilage, Articular"[Mesh] OR anatomic model*[tiab] OR anatomical model*[tiab] OR ex-vivo[tiab] OR in-vitro[tiab] OR cadav*[tiab] OR dead donor[tiab] OR corpse[tiab] OR corpses[tiab] OR human tissue[tiab] OR human tissues[tiab] OR sawbone[tiab] OR synbone[tiab] OR sawbones[tiab] OR synbones[tiab] OR saw bone[tiab] OR syn-bone[tiab] OR saw bones[tiab] OR syn-bones[tiab] OR synthetic bone[tiab] OR artificial bone[tiab] OR artificial bones[tiab] OR bone-substitute*[tiab] OR metallic humerus[tiab] OR Polyethylene glenoid[tiab] OR artificial glenoid[tiab] OR glenoid prosthesis[tiab] OR glenoid prostheses[tiab] OR glenoid component*[tiab] OR glenoid sphere*[tiab] OR polyethylene liner*[tiab])

AND ("Models, Anatomic"[Mesh:NoExp] OR "Accelerometry"[Mesh:NoExp] OR acceleromet*[tiab] OR simulat*[tiab] OR anatomic model*[tiab] OR anatomical model*[tiab] OR device[tiab] OR apparatus[tiab] OR experiment*[tiab] OR testing[tiab] OR test[tiab] OR tests[tiab] OR cable tension[tiab] OR cable pulley[tiab] OR cable tensions[tiab] OR force gauge[tiab] OR motion analysis system[tiab] OR motion analysis systems[tiab])

AND ("Shoulder Joint"[Mesh] OR "Shoulder"[Mesh] OR Humerus[Mesh] OR "Scapula"[Mesh] OR shoulder[tiab] OR shoulders[tiab] OR GH-joint[tiab] OR glenoid[tiab] OR glenoidal[tiab] OR glenohumeral[tiab] OR Glensphere[tiab] OR scapula[tiab] OR acromion[tiab] OR acromial[tiab] OR coracoid[tiab] OR coracoidal[tiab] OR humerus[tiab] OR humeral[tiab] OR "Rotator Cuff"[Mesh] OR "Deltoid Muscle"[Mesh] OR deltoid[tiab] OR rotator cuff[tiab] OR supraspinatus[tiab] OR subscapularis[tiab] OR infraspinatus[tiab] OR teres minor[tiab] OR scapulothoracic[tiab])

AND ("Joint Instability"[Mesh] OR "mechanical Phenomena"[Mesh:NoExp] OR "Biomechanical Phenomena"[Mesh:NoExp] OR "Compressive Strength"[Mesh:NoExp] OR "Friction"[Mesh:NoExp] OR "Kinetics"[Mesh:NoExp] OR "Lifting"[Mesh] OR "Shear Strength"[Mesh] OR "Stress, Mechanical"[Mesh:NoExp] OR "Pliability"[Mesh:NoExp] OR "Torsion, Mechanical"[Mesh] OR "Mechanical Tests"[Mesh:NoExp] OR "Pressure"[Mesh:NoExp] OR "Decompression"[Mesh:NoExp] OR "Movement"[Mesh:NoExp] OR "Range of Motion, Articular"[Mesh:NoExp] OR "Motion"[Mesh:NoExp] OR "Acceleration"[Mesh] OR "Rotation"[Mesh:NoExp] OR biomechanic*[tiab] OR mechanic*[tiab] OR kinematics[tiab] OR kinetic[tiab] OR kinetics[tiab] OR mass[tiab] OR "contact stress"[tiab] OR "shear stress"[tiab] OR lifting[tiab] OR Pliability[tiab] OR pressure[tiab] OR decompress*[tiab] OR compress*[tiab] OR gravity[tiab] OR "stress strain relationship"[tiab] OR motion[tiab] OR movement[tiab] OR movements[tiab] OR mobility[tiab] OR accelerat*[tiab] OR decelerat*[tiab] OR dynamic[tiab] OR dynamics[tiab] OR dynamical[tiab] OR glenohumeral translation[tiab] OR cross-shear[tiab] OR wear rate[tiab] OR wear rates[tiab] OR implant prediction[tiab] OR joint contact force[tiab] OR joint contact strength[tiab] OR joint pressure[tiab] OR shear strength[tiab] OR shear force*[tiab] OR torque[tiab] OR joint force[tiab] OR joint strength[tiab] OR muscle force*[tiab] OR muscle strength[tiab] OR muscle optimization[tiab] OR muscle optimisation[tiab] OR abduction [tiab] OR adduction[tiab] OR rotation[tiab] OR flexion[tiab] OR elevation[tiab] OR circumduction[tiab] OR Instability[tiab] OR stability[tiab] OR Compressive Strength[tiab] OR Friction[tiab])

NOT ("animals"[MeSH Terms] NOT "humans"[MeSH Terms])

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('Anatomic Model'/de OR 'Cadaver'/de OR 'In Vitro Study'/de OR 'human tissue'/de OR 'Ex Vivo Study'/de OR 'articular cartilage'/de OR 'sawbone'/exp OR 'sawbones'/exp OR 'artificial bone'/exp OR "anatomic model*":ti,ab OR "anatomical model*":ti,ab OR ex-vivo:ti,ab OR in-vitro:ti,ab OR cadav*:ti,ab OR "dead donor":ti,ab OR corpse:ti,ab OR corpses:ti,ab OR "human tissue":ti,ab OR "human tissues":ti,ab OR sawbone:ti,ab OR synbone:ti,ab OR sawbones:ti,ab OR synbones:ti,ab OR "saw bone":ti,ab OR syn-bone:ti,ab OR "saw bones":ti,ab OR syn-bones:ti,ab OR "synthetic bone":ti,ab OR "artificial bone":ti,ab OR "artificial bones":ti,ab OR bone-substitute*:ti,ab OR "metallic humerus":ti,ab OR "Polyethylene glenoid":ti,ab OR "artificial glenoid":ti,ab OR "glenoid prosthesis":ti,ab OR "glenoid prostheses":ti,ab OR "glenoid component*":ti,ab OR "glenoid sphere*":ti,ab OR "polyethylene liner*":ti,ab)

AND ('Anatomic Model'/de OR 'simulator'/de OR 'accelerometer'/de OR 'force gauge'/de OR 'motion analysis system'/de OR "anatomic model*":ti,ab OR "anatomical model*":ti,ab OR simulat*:ti,ab OR device:ti,ab OR apparatus:ti,ab OR experiment*:ti,ab OR

testing:ti,ab OR test:ti,ab OR tests:ti,ab OR "cable tension":ti,ab OR "cable tensions":ti,ab OR "cable pulley":ti,ab OR accelerometer:ti,ab OR accelerometers:ti,ab OR "force gauge":ti,ab OR "motion analysis system":ti,ab OR "motion analysis systems":ti,ab)

AND ('Shoulder'/exp OR 'humerus'/exp OR 'scapulothoracic joint'/de OR 'glenohumeral ligament'/de OR shoulder:ti,ab OR shoulders:ti,ab OR GH-joint:ti,ab OR glenoid:ti,ab OR glenoidal:ti,ab OR glenohumeral:ti,ab OR Glenosphere:ti,ab OR scapula:ti,ab OR acromion:ti,ab OR acromial:ti,ab OR coracoid:ti,ab OR coracoidal:ti,ab OR humerus:ti,ab OR humeral:ti,ab OR Scapulothoracic:ti,ab OR 'subscapularis tendon'/de OR 'supraspinatus muscle tendon'/de OR 'supraspinatus tendon'/de OR 'infraspinatus tendon'/de OR deltoid:ti,ab OR "rotator cuff":ti,ab OR supraspinatus:ti,ab OR subscapularis:ti,ab OR infraspinatus:ti,ab OR "teres minor":t i,ab)

AND ('Joint Instability'/de OR 'Biomechanics'/de OR 'Compressive Strength'/de OR 'Friction'/de OR 'Kinetics'/de OR 'acceleration'/de OR 'deceleration'/de OR 'Shear Strength'/de OR 'Mechanical Stress'/exp OR 'Pliability'/de OR 'Mechanical Torsion'/de OR 'torque'/exp OR 'Mechanical Test'/de OR 'Pressure'/de OR 'movement (physiology)'/de OR 'Range of Motion'/de OR 'Motion'/de OR 'rotation'/de OR 'joint contact force'/de OR 'joint pressure'/de OR 'dynamics'/de OR 'compression'/de OR 'decompression'/de OR 'gravity'/de OR 'stress strain relationship'/de OR 'force'/de OR 'kinematics'/de OR 'mass'/de OR 'contact stress'/de OR 'shear stress'/de OR 'abduction'/de OR 'adduction'/de OR 'adduction muscle contracture'/de OR 'arm movement'/de OR 'arm exercise'/de OR 'joint mobility'/de OR 'joint stability'/de OR biomechanic*:ti,ab OR mechanic*:ti,ab OR kinematics:ti,ab OR kinetic:ti,ab OR kinetics:ti,ab OR mass:ti,ab OR "contact stress":ti,ab OR "shear stress":ti,ab OR lifting:ti,ab OR Pliability:ti,ab OR pressure:ti,ab OR decomp res*:ti,ab OR compress*:ti,ab OR gravity:ti,ab OR "stress strain relationship":ti,ab OR motion:ti,ab OR movement:ti,ab OR movements:ti,ab OR mobility:ti,ab OR accelerat*:ti,ab OR decelerat*:ti,ab OR dynamic:ti,ab OR dynamics:ti,ab OR dynamical:ti,ab OR "glenohumeral translation":ti,ab OR cross-shear:ti,ab OR "wear rate":ti,ab OR "wear rates":ti,ab OR "implant prediction":ti,ab OR "Joint contact force":ti,ab OR "joint contact strength":ti,ab OR "joint pressure":ti,ab OR "Shear Strength":ti,ab OR "shear force*":ti,ab OR torque:ti,ab OR "Joint force":ti,ab OR "joint strength":ti,ab OR "muscle force*":ti,ab OR "muscle strength":ti,ab OR "Muscle optimization":ti,ab OR "Muscle optimisation":ti,ab OR abduction:ti,ab OR adduction:ti,ab OR rotation:ti,ab OR flexion:ti,ab OR elevation:ti,ab OR circumduction:ti,ab OR "Instability":ti,ab OR "stability":ti,ab OR "Compressive Strength":ti,ab OR Friction:ti,ab)

NOT (('animal'/de OR 'animal experiment'/exp OR 'nonhuman'/de) NOT ('human'/exp OR 'human experiment'/de))

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AND (acceleromet* OR simulat* OR "anatomic model*" OR "anatomical model*" OR device OR apparatus OR experiment* OR testing OR test OR tests OR "cable tension" OR "cable pulley" OR "cable tensions" OR "force gauge" OR "motion analysis system" OR "motion analysis systems")

AND (shoulder OR shoulders OR GH-joint OR glenoid OR glenoidal OR glenohumeral OR Glenosphere OR scapula OR acromion OR acromial OR coracoid OR coracoidal OR humerus OR humeral OR deltoid OR "rotator cuff" OR supraspinatus OR subscapularis OR infraspinatus OR "teres minor" OR scapulothoracic)

AND (biomechanic* OR mechanic* OR kinematics OR kinetic OR kinetics OR mass OR "contact stress" OR "shear stress" OR lifting OR Pliability OR pressure OR decompress* OR compress* OR gravity OR "stress strain relationship" OR motion OR movement OR

movements OR mobility OR accelerat* OR decelerat* OR dynamic OR dynamics OR dynamical OR "glenohumeral translation" OR cross-shear OR "wear rate" OR "wear rates" OR "implant prediction" OR "joint contact force" OR "joint contact strength" OR "joint pressure" OR "shear strength" OR "shear force*" OR torque OR "joint force" OR "joint strength" OR "muscle force*" OR "muscle strength" OR "muscle optimization" OR "muscle optimisation" OR abduction OR adduction OR rotation OR flexion OR elevation OR circumduction OR Instability OR stability OR "Compressive Strength" OR Friction))

Note: TS searches in the Abstract, Title, and/or Keywords fields of a record;

Indexes=

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- Conference Proceedings Citation Index- Social Science & Humanities (CPCI-SSH) --1990-present
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- Current Chemical Reactions (CCR-EXPANDED) --1985-present (Includes Institut National de la Propriete Industrielle structure data back to 1840)
- Index Chemicus (IC) --1993-present

Timespan=All years